

VIGILANCE

Content

The purpose of this guide is to assist the Consortium in using correctly the VIGILANCE logo. It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers, and others employed to produce branded items to design and create VIGILANCE communications material. In order to maintain the integrity of the VIGILANCE project brand identity, it is important to apply all the given instructions properly.

- 1 Logo Specifics
- 2 Logo Versions
- 3 Clear space
- 4 Logo Misuse
- 5-6 Colour Palette
- 7 Typography
- 8-9 Typography in Use

Logomark

Our logo is the face of VIGILANCE - the primary visual expression that we use to identify ourselves. Meaning that **we need to be careful** to use it correctly and to do so consistently.

Primary Logo

Logo Versions

VIGILANCE Logo **should be used mostly** with the Vigilance Blue and Vigilance Cyan . The negative Vigilance logo can be used on dark image backgrounds with high contrast between them.

Sometimes depending on background or application specific occasions can be used in Vigilance Cyan.

Versatile Intelligent aGents
for Interconnected Ledgers
& Autonomous Next-gen
Cybersecurity Ecosystems

Primary Logo with full project name

VIGILANCE

Primary Logo on Vigilance Cyan

VIGILANCE

Negative Vigilance Logo

VIGILANCE

Vertical Vigilance Logo

Clear space

Clear space is the area surrounding the global signature and icon that must be kept free of any elements, including text, graphics, borders, or other logos. **The minimum clear space** required for the preferred global signature is equal to 1/2 the height and width of the Vigilance Icon.

Logo Misuse

It is important that the appearance of the logo remains consistent. The logo **should not be misinterpreted, modified, or added to.** No attempt should be made to alter the logo in any way. Its orientation, colour and composition should remain as indicated in this document.

Do not distort or alter the proportions of the logo

Do not add contours to the logo

Do not add a drop shadow to the logo

Do not change any elements or colour

Do not use any other fonts

Do not rotate the logo to any angle

Our Colour Palette

The colours selected for the Vigilance signature **reflect the logo's values**. The colors have been specifically chosen to represent the brand and should not be altered under any circumstance.

Primary Colour
#102d69

Secondary Colour
#00afdb

Text Colour
#000000

Highlight Colour
#a61979

Vigilance
Blue

Hex #102D69
RGB 16, 45, 105
CMYK 100, 90, 30, 15
Pantone 287 C

Vigilance
Cyan

Hex #00AFDB
RGB 0, 175, 219
CMYK 75, 10, 5, 0
Pantone 305 C

Vigilance
Magenta

Hex #A61979
RGB 166, 25, 121
CMYK 40, 100, 10, 0
Pantone 247 C

Neutral
Black

Hex #000000
RGB 0 0 0
CMYK 0 0 0 100
Pantone Neutral Black

The Typeface Family

The **primary font is**

Commissioner (*Google font*)

and it has 3 weights:

Light, Regular & Bold

You can find the font here:

<https://bit.ly/302KjAQ>

When to Use

Commissioner (Regular) is to be used for all forms of standard body text.

Commissioner (Bold & Light) is to be used for Buttons, Titles and Highlight important points.

Commissioner (Light)

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890!@£\$%^&*()

Commissioner (Regular)

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890!@£\$%^&*()

Commissioner (Bold)

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890!@£\$%^&*()

Web site Text

40px H1 Title

32px H2 Title

26px H3 SubTitle

20px H4 SubTitle

20px H4 SubTitle normal

16px Paragraph text bold

16px Paragraph text

Buttons

PrimaryCTA button

Secondary CTA button

Basic button

Secondary button

Complimentary button

Email Signature

Full Name _____ 16pt - Commissioner Bold - Colour: Black

Job Title _____ 14pt - Commissioner Italic- Colour: #00sfdb

e: name@vigilance.eu _____ 14pt - Commissioner Regular/Bold - Colour: #102d69

m: 6944 44 44 44

VIGILANCE _____

150px Width

*Technopolis ICT Business Park,
Pylaia, Thessaloniki, Greece*

13pt - Commissioner Italic- Colour: #102d69

e: info@vigilance.eu

www.vigilance.eu

Thank you for the proper use of Vigilance brand.

For more info about proper use please contact:
ouzounidis@ece.auth.com